

METHODOLOGIES FOR INVESTIGATING OCCUPATIONAL ACCIDENTS AND THEIR USE IN OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY RESEARCH. LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to review the main studies published on occupational accidents to recognize, classify and describe the scientific methodologies used.

To achieve the objective set we used a method that has already been implemented and validated, consisting of an extensive review of international scientific literature related to the methodologies for investigating accidents in occupational health and safety. Then, to assess the importance of these methodologies, we analyzed the number of times the selected publications are cited and the impact factor of the journal where it was published.

The results of this review show that many different investigation methodologies have been developed over the last few decades. These methodologies cover different areas of application, qualities and limitations, with the understanding that a thorough accident investigation requires a combination of different activities included in these methods. This study describes which methodologies have been used the most in the field of occupational accident investigations. A total of 35 different methodologies were identified. This study reveals that, even to this day, there are not many methodologies available with a single focus on the field of occupational health and safety. On the other hand, in order to develop and advance in the application of occupational accident investigation techniques, it would be advisable to promote studies that verify the proper selection and use of methodologies in real cases of occupational accidents.